

ROLE OF SAHACHARADI YAPANA BASTI IN KATIGRAHA (LUMBAR SPONDYLOSIS)- A REVIEW ARTICLE

Drishti Kotiyal^{*1}, Arvind Gupta², Roopali Barmola³, Akshay Verma⁴

¹P.G Scholar, ²Professor and HOD, ³Asst. Professor, ⁴Asst. Professor
Department of Panchakarma, Himalayiya Ayurvedic (P.G) Medical College and Hospital, Fatehpura Tanda via
Doiwala, Dehradun.

*Corresponding Author: Drishti Kotiyal

P.G Scholar, Department of Panchakarma, Himalayiya Ayurvedic (P.G) Medical College and Hospital, Fatehpura Tanda via
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ABSTRACT

Low back pain is one of the most prevalent musculoskeletal disorders, affecting individuals across all age groups and significantly impairing routine activities. Low back pain affects 65-85% of adults at some point in their lives.^[1] Among its various causes, lumbar spondylosis is the most common, primarily resulting from degenerative changes in the intervertebral discs, facet joints, and vertebral bodies. Modern management strategies are mainly aimed at alleviating pain and improving mobility. However, these approaches often provide only temporary relief and are associated with adverse effects. In Ayurveda, this condition is closely correlated with *Katigraha*, which presents with pain (*Shoola*) and stiffness (*Stambha*) in the *Katipradesha* (Lumbar region) due to aggravated *Vata Dosha*. Classical texts such as Shodhala's *Kayachikitsa* describe *Katigraha* under *Vataroga Adhikara* and further classify it into *Saama* and *Nirama* types depending on the presence of *Ama* (toxins). For *Vatavyadhi*, *Basti* therapy is regarded as *Ardhachikitsa* and holds a prime position, as *Vata* is the chief causative factor in *katigraha*. *Acharya Charaka* also emphasized *Bastikarma* in the *Samanya Chikitsa* of *Vatavyadhi*. *Yapana Basti* is a specialized form of *Basti* therapy, distinguished by its dual action of *Shodhana* (purification) and *Brimhana* (nourishment). *Sahacharadi Yapana Basti*, through its unique formulation, helps pacify aggravated *Vata Dosha*, prevent degenerative changes, and provide strength to the lumbar spine and surrounding structures. Unlike conventional *Basti* types, it can be administered for extended periods, making it especially valuable in managing chronic degenerative disorders such as *Katigraha*. In this context, the present article aims to evaluate the therapeutic role of *Sahacharadi Yapana Basti* in the effective management of *Katigraha*.

KEYWORDS: *Katigraha*, Lumbar spondylosis, *Basti*, *Yapana Basti*, *Shodhana*, *Brimhana*.

INTRODUCTION

Lumbar spondylosis is one of the most prevalent degenerative conditions of the spine, primarily affecting the lower back. It is characterized by progressive degeneration of the intervertebral discs, narrowing of disc spaces, endplate sclerosis, and the formation of osteophytes, leading to chronic pain, stiffness, and reduced mobility. Although more common in the elderly due to age-related degeneration, Lumbar spondylosis is increasingly reported in younger populations, largely attributable to lifestyle factors such as prolonged sitting, poor posture, excessive screen exposure, occupational strain, frequent travel, and sedentary habits. The rapid pace of modern industrialization and technological dependence has further contributed to early onset and progression of spinal disorders.

Diagnosis of Lumbar spondylosis is based on a detailed clinical history, physical examination, and imaging

modalities such as X-ray, MRI, CT, and EMG. Current management in modern medicine is largely symptomatic, aiming to reduce pain, restore function, and delay further degeneration through lifestyle modifications, pharmacotherapy—including non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), muscle relaxants, and corticosteroid injections—and surgical intervention in severe cases. However, these approaches often provide only temporary relief and may be associated with side effects on long-term use.

In Ayurveda, the Lumbar region is termed *Katipradesha*, and its disorders are closely correlated with *Katigraha*, which presents with pain and restricted mobility. In *Gadanigraha*, it is classified as either *Saamvat* and *Nirama Vata* goes to the *Katipradesha* and lodges there and causes *Katigraha*.^[2] The underlying pathology involves *Vata* vitiation, primarily due to *Dhatukshaya* (degenerative changes) and *Margavarodha* (channel

obstruction)^[3], with *Dhatukshaya* considered the key factor. Unwholesome dietary and lifestyle habits, such as frequent consumption of *Ruksha* (dry), *Sheeta* (cold), and *Laghu* (light) foods, together with *Ratrijagarana* (night awakening) and *Vegadharana* (suppression of natural urges), contribute to depletion of tissues and aggravation of *Vata Dosha*. The *Ruksha Guna* of vitiated *Vata* depletes *Kapha* in the joints, reducing lubrication and weakening *Sandhi Bandhana* (joint structures). These structurally weak joints (*Khavaigunyayukta Sandhi*) in the *Katipradesha* then become the site for localization of aggravated *Vata*, producing stiffness and pain

characteristic of *Katigraha*.

Improper food intake, especially during indigestion or excessive use of *Guru* (heavy), *Shita* (cold), *Ruksha* (dry), and *Vishtambhi* (obstructive) diets, further promotes *Ama* formation. This disturbs *Agni*, provokes *Doshas*, and hampers *Rasa Dhatu* metabolism. Weakening of both *Jatharagni* and *Dhatvagni* results in *Srotorodha* (channel obstruction), predisposing to *Vata* aggravation and manifestation of pain (*Ruk*) and stiffness (*Stambha*) in the lumbar joints.

Samprapti Ghatak of Katigraha

Dosha	Vata Kapha	Apaan vayu
		Shleshak kaph, avlambhak kaph
Dushya	Dhatu	Asthi, Ras
	Updhatu	Kandra, Snaayu
Udbhavsthan	Pakvashya	
Vyaktasthana	Kati	
Marga	Madhyamrogamarga	
Srotas	Ras, Asthi, Purishvaha	
Srotodushti	Sanga	
Agni	Madhyama	

Chikitsa of Katigraha

Katigraha is classified as a *Vataja Nanatmaja Vyadhi*^[4], with *Vata Dosha* as the primary factor in its pathogenesis. *Gadanigrahakara* describes it as a disorder where vitiated *Vata* localizes in the *Katipradesha*, producing pain and stiffness, while *Sushruta* highlights that aggravated *Vata* in the lumbar *Sandhi* leads to stiffness (*Hanti Sandhi*), pain (*Sandhishoola*), and degeneration (*Asthishosha*).^[5] *Acharya Charaka* states vitiation of *Vata* causes *Asthishoola*, *Sandhishoola*, *Parvbheda*, *Manskshaya*, *Balkshaya*, etc. (*Asthipradoshaj vikara*).^[6]

Being a *Vatavyadhi*, its management follows the principles of *Samanya Vatopakrama*. The main therapeutic measures include *Vata Shamaka Ahara* (dietary regulation), *Snehana* (oleation), *Swedana* (sudation), *Mridu Samshodhana* (mild purificatory therapies), *Bahir Parimarjana* (external treatments), and especially *Basti* therapy, considered the most effective for pacifying *Vata* and managing *Katigraha*. *Basti* therapy eliminates accumulated *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*, *Mutra*, and *Anila*, thereby promoting bodily stability and enhancing *Shukra Dhatu*. By expelling morbid *Doshas* from the entire body, *Basti* is considered highly effective in restoring balance and is described as a therapy capable of alleviating a wide range of disorders.^[7]

Concept of Sahacharadi Yapana Basti in Katigraha

It is a type of mild *Niruha Basti*, which is having the property to support life and longevity.^[8] It is known for its *Balya* (strengthening), *Rasayana* (rejuvenating), and *Vata-Kapha Shamak* (balancing) effects. It acts via systemic absorption through the colon, replenishing depleted tissues and pacifying aggravated *Vata*

Sahachara alleviates *Vata* and supports neuromuscular coordination, reducing stiffness and pain. *Bala* nourishes and strengthens muscles, ligaments, and connective tissues, thereby enhancing spinal stability. *Sariva* acts on *Raktadhatu*, improving circulation and supporting tissue repair. The unctuous media of milk, ghee, and oils counter the *Ruksha Guna* of aggravated *Vata*, restoring lubrication within vertebral joints and preventing further wear and tear. Additionally, their *Brimhana* property helps replenish depleted tissues, while *Rasayana* effects promote overall vitality. Through these synergistic actions, *Sahacharadi Yapana Basti* not only pacifies *Vata* but also provides structural nourishment and resilience to the lumbar spine and surrounding ligaments, effectively addressing both the symptomatic and degenerative aspects of *Katigraha* (lumbar spondylosis).

Sahacharadi yapana basti content and their properties

Name	Latin name	Family	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Vipaka	Karma
Sahachara	Barleria prionitis	Acanthaceae	Tikta, Madhur	Laghu	Ushna	Katu	Kaphvatashamak, Vednasthapan, Varnshodhan, Kusthaghana
Bala	Sida cordifolia	Malvaceae	Madhura	Snigdha, Picchila	Sheeta	Madhura	Tridoshghana, Balya, Vrushya, Vatanuloman
Darbha	Desmostachya bipinnata	Graminaceae	Madhura, Kashaya	Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	Tridoshghana, Mootral, Rasayana, Ruchya
Sariva	Hemidesmus indica	Asclepiadaceae	Madhura	Snigdha, Guru	Sheeta	Madhura	Tridoshghana, Shukral, Vrushya, Grahi, krumighana
Madanphala	Randia spinosa	Rubiaceae	Madhura, Kshaya, Tikta, Katu	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Vednasthapak, Shothhar, Nadishamak
Yashtimadhu	Glycyrrhizza glabra	Fabaceae	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	Vednasthapak, Nadibalya
Pippali	Piper longum	Piperaceae	Tikta	Laghu, Snigdha, Tikshna	Sheeta	Madhura	Vatanuloman, Shoolaprashman
Til tail	-	-	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha, Sukshma	Ushna	Madhura	Vata shamak, kaphapittahara
Go-dugdh	-	-	Madhura	Snigdha, Mridu, Shlakshana	Sheeta	Madhura	Vatapitta shamak, kaphavardak, rasayan

Ingredients of Sahacharadi yapana basti

Ingredients	Quantity
Honey	70ml
Saindhav	5gms
Murchita til tail	70ml
kalka	15gms
Sahacharadi ksheer	320ml

DISCUSSION

- In Ayurveda, *Vata* is considered the prime causative factor in painful and degenerative disorders, and therefore *Basti* therapy is described as *Ardhachikitsa*.^[9] for the management of *Vatavyadhi*. *Acharya Charaka* has emphasized *Bastikarma* in the *Samanya Chikitsa* of *Vatavyadhi*, highlighting its systemic action in pacifying aggravated *Vata*.
- Yapana Basti* holds particular significance in chronic conditions such as *Katigraha* where *Vata vitiation* and tissue degeneration predominate.
- Sahacharadi Yapana Basti*^[10] by virtue of its ingredients offers a unique blend of *Vatahara*, *Balya*, *Brimhana*, and *Rasayana* properties.
- Several ingredients of *Sahacharadi Yapana Basti* possess *Madhura*, *Snigdha*, and *Ushna* properties, which effectively pacify aggravated *Vata*. *Go-dugdh* (cow's milk) and *Tila Taila* (sesame oil) exhibit *Brimhana* (nourishing) effects that strengthen and replenish *Asthi Dhatu*, thereby supporting bone health and countering degenerative changes.

CONCLUSION

Katigraha (lumbar spondylosis) is a chronic degenerative disorder primarily caused by *Vata vitiation*, presenting with pain, stiffness, and restricted mobility. While modern therapies focus mainly on symptomatic relief, they often fail to prevent progression and may cause adverse effects with prolonged use. *Sahacharadi Yapana Basti*, owing to its *Vatahara*, *Balya*, *Brimhana*, and *Rasayana* properties, not only alleviates symptoms but also nourishes and strengthens the lumbar spine and surrounding structures. Thus, it offers a holistic, sustainable, and effective therapeutic approach in the management of *Katigraha*.

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